

Reliability for Cluster-based Ad-hoc Networks

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SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

The Mobile Ad-hoc Wireless Network (MAWN) is a new and emerging network scheme that is being employed in a variety of applications. The MAWN varies from traditional networks because it is a self-forming and dynamic network. The MAWN is free of infrastructure and as such only the mobile nodes comprise the network. Nodes communicate either directly or through other nodes. To do so each node acts as source, destination, and relay. The virtue of a MAWN is the flexibility this provides however the challenge for reliability analyses is also brought about by this unique feature. The variability and volatility of the MAWN's configuration makes typical reliability methods (e.g. reliability block diagram) inappropriate because no single structure or configuration represents all manifestations of a MAWN. For this reason, new methods are being developed to analyze the reliability of this new networking technology. New published methods adapt to this feature by treating the configuration probabilistically or by inclusion of mobility models. This paper expands upon these works by modifying the problem formulation to utilize a Monte Carlo simulation technique for the reliability analysis of a cluster-based MAWN. The cluster-based MAWN is deployed in applications with constraints or limits on the networking resources such as bandwidth and energy. This paper presents the problem's formulation, a discussion of applicable reliability metrics for the MAWN, and illustration of the method through the analysis of several example networks. Within this paper, a new and innovative use of the general MC simulation approach will be described that allows the practitioner to quickly approximate the reliability of a MAWN and understand the interactions of the characteristics that describe the MAWN; namely node reliability, node mobility, and transport (cluster) layer design. This paper is a follow on from one presented at RAMS 2007.

1 INTRODUCTION

The mobile ad-hoc wireless network (MAWN) is emerging scheme that differs with traditional infrastructure based wired and wireless networks. Originally developed for the Department of Defense (DoD), the MAWN is enabled small, mobile wireless devices. In a MAWN, all nodes are mobile and have the capability to send, receive, and relay messages. This allows for communication through an

intermediary (relay) node. The cluster-based MAWN is a specific type of MAWN which provides benefits for bandwidth, and energy constrained MAWN by logically grouping nodes into clusters.

Several network reliability methods available in the literature consider networks with unreliable nodes and links but these methods assume the configuration of the network is known *a priori* – not so for a MAWN. The authors have published several papers regarding MAWN reliability and this is a continuation of that research.

Assumptions

- Nodes are a member of one and only one local subnet
- Each local subnet has the same probability of link existence since these links are enabled by identical radios
- Nodes may be a member of any, none, or all back-bone subnets.
- Nodes in the same back-bone subnet have a constant probability of link existence, however, this may vary by back-bone due to the different technologies (e.g. satellite versus terrestrial).

2 RELATED WORK

2.1 Network Reliability

Two-terminal Reliability (2TR) is the popular metric for many reliability problems involving networks. For complex networks the efficient analysis methods are based on minimal path set enumeration and Monte Carlo Simulation [1-3]. Feo and Johnson [2] provide a partial factoring technique that provides confidence bounds on two-terminal reliability. Rocco & Moreno [3] propose Monte Carlo methods that were developed to analyze two-terminal reliability using cellular automata to improve efficiencies. Similarly, Rocco and Zio [4] modified those methods to compute All-terminal (ATR).

2.2 Ad-hoc Networks

Generally, research for ad-hoc networks focuses on optimization of network protocols for mobility of the nodes [5]. Similar to the concept of frequency re-use popularized by cellular networks, clustering of the MAWN improves bandwidth availability. The concept is, by segregating the network into several smaller networks, termed local sub-nets, the bandwidth is split amongst fewer nodes. Ghosh [6] et al

refer to back-bone nodes as “gateways”; describing their role as “inter cluster data transfer takes place through cluster gateways.” Krishanan and Starobinski [7] inform that the appropriate clustering of nodes aids for bandwidth improvements and power efficiency.

2.3 Wireless and Ad-hoc Network Reliability

To date, Cook and Ramirez-Marquez [8-12] have focused on a single cohesive MAWN rather than the cluster-based MAWN. The Monte Carlo simulation method in [8] is adapted in this paper to accommodate the more flexible and scalable cluster-based MAWN. In this current paper, the authors will feature a probabilistic description of the network’s configuration. Contrastingly, in [9,12] the authors embed a mobility model within a Monte Carlo reliability approximation to reach the same goal.

3 TECHNICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Let $G(N,L)$ define a MAWN where the network nodes are defined by the vector N , where n represents number of nodes in the network and the links are defined by the matrix $L(t)$. The individual node status for node i is defined as n_i , where $i=1,2,\dots,n$ and n_i are elements of N . Since the nodes in the network are not perfectly reliable, they may take on two states, operational and failed. Let $n_i(t)=1$ if the node is operational at time t and $n_i(t)=0$ if node i has failed by time t . The reliability of the i^{th} node is given by $r_i(t)$ where $r_i(t)=P(n_i(t)=1)$.

In a cluster-based MAWN $G(N,L)$ is composed of several local subnets which will be defined as $G_s^L(N_s^L, L_s^L)$ representing local subnet s , $s=1,\dots,S$. Like $G(N,L)$, $G_s^L(N_s^L, L_s^L)$ is comprised of N_s^L , its corresponding set of nodes (with $N_s^L \subset N$ and $N_u^L \cap N_v^L = \emptyset$) and L_s^L , a link matrix of size $n \times n$, representing the possible states of the links between the nodes of the subnet. this type of network, Figure 1 illustrates one possible configuration of one eight node local subnet (with its corresponding connectivity matrix) at some point in time. In this case, the local subnet considered is $G_1^L(N_1^L, L_1^L)$, with node set $N_1^L = \{1,\dots,8\}$ and L_1^L (a 24 x 24 matrix). It is important to note that in Figure 1, the representation of L_1^L illustrates only the status of the connections among the links nodes contained in N_1^L .

To illustrate the multiple clusters of a MAWN, Figure 2 presents possible configurations of two additional local subnets and a back-bone subnet. Henceforth, the node membership in subnet(s) will be referred to as the *design*.

The bringing together the local subnets is the Back-bone network(s). For these subnets, let $G_b^B(N_b^B, L_b^B)$ define back-bone subnet b ($b=1,\dots,B$) with node set N_b^B and connectivity matrix L_b^B of size $n \times n$.

Based on the previous description of local and back-bone subnets, $G(N,L)$ can be understood as the union of these network into a cohesive network. In this respect,

$$N = \bigcup_{s=1}^S N_s^L \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Local Subnet

Figure 2. Full Network

$$L = \sum_{s=1}^S L_s^L + \sum_{b=1}^B L_b^B. \quad (1a)$$

In this paper, the reliability of a cluster-based MAWN will be approximated via Monte Carlo simulation. In this respect, the results of each simulation run q will represent an instantiation of the MAWN and specifically of its links. Thus, matrix $L(q)$ is formed of elements $l_{ij}(q)$, dictated by matrices $L_s^L(q)$ and $L_b^B(q)$, representing the existence of a link between mobile nodes i and j where $l_{ij}(q) = 1$ if a wireless link exists between nodes i and j and, zero otherwise. Therefore, each possible configuration of the subnets at a specific run q will be notated as $G_s^L(N_s^L, L_s^L(q))$ and $G_b^B(N_b^B, L_b^B(q))$. Accordingly, the networks shown in the preceding figures along with their links and link matrices should be interpreted as possible configurations of a single run of the MC simulation.

Additionally, as in [8] the probability of link existence is set between $0 \dots 1$. Here, we sub and superscript this metric to differentiate the subnets; λ_s^L and λ_b^B for each local subsidiary network s and each back-bone network b , respectively.

A node represents the host platform (vehicle, person, etc) on which one or more the radio(s) are installed. Each subnet uses a radio, therefore nodes that are members of both local and back-bone subnets have multiple radios. The reliability of

the radios is denoted as r_b^B representing the reliability of the radio on any node in back-bone b or r_s^L for the local subnet s . The state of the radios is represented by n_{ib}^B and n_{is}^L accordingly; so $r_b^B = \Pr(n_{ib}^B=1)$ and $r_s^L = 1 - \Pr(n_{ib}^B=0)$.

The probability of link existence for node pair ij is conditional upon the radios of that node pair operating, giving: $\lambda_{ij}^L = \Pr(l_{ij}=1 | n_{is}^L, n_{js}^L=1) \forall$ pairs ij having membership in local subnet s .

3.1 Monte Carlo Method

The MC simulation to approximate the reliability metrics is as follows: The specified number of runs is given as Q . For each run q ($q=1, \dots, Q$) the state of each node's radio(s) is simulated using r_s^L and r_b^B while $\mathbf{L}_s^L(q)$ and $\mathbf{L}_b^B(q)$ are generated using the probability values obtained offline for λ_s^L and λ_b^B . The matrices, $\mathbf{L}_s^L(q)$ and $\mathbf{L}_b^B(q)$ are then combined to obtain $\mathbf{L}(q)$. Next, $\mathbf{L}(q)$ is analyzed via a breadth first search (BFS) algorithm using node 1 as the root (the node where the BFS is initiated) or if failed, using the first operational node in increasing order (i.e. node 2, then node 3, etc...). The results of the BFS are loaded in $\mathbf{\Lambda}(q)$, a vector where, if there exists a path from the root (node 1) to node i in run q then $\Lambda_i(q) = 1$, else = 0.

$$2\hat{TR}_m = \frac{\sum_{q=1}^Q \mathbf{\Lambda}_n(q)}{Q} \quad (2)$$

$$A\hat{TR}_m = \frac{\sum_{q=1}^Q \prod_{i=1}^n \Lambda_i(q)}{Q} \quad (3)$$

$$Ao\hat{TR}_m = \frac{\sum_{q=1}^Q test(q)}{Q} \quad (4)$$

$AoTR$ as defined is the probability that all operational nodes are connected. So, to measure $AoTR$ for a simulation run consider a variable $test = 1$ if for all nodes that are operational ($n_i = 1$) they are also connected ($\Lambda_i = 1$). The simulation process is depicted in the form of a process flow diagram in Figure3.

Several examples are analyzed to depict the capabilities of this method. All networks analyzed have 24 nodes, and the following parameters are used throughout the examples: $\lambda_s^L = 0.7 \forall s$, $\lambda_1^B = 0.5$, and $\lambda_2^B = 0.95$. Finally, the reliability of the radios is also assumed constant for all designs analyzed with $r_s^L = 0.95$ for all local radios, $r_1^B = 0.9$ for the radios in the first back-bone subnet and $r_2^B = 0.85$ for the radios enabling the second (satellite based) back-bone subnet. Modified will be the design of the local and back-bone networks.

Table 1 shows the local subnet design that are used for the first five examples. Table 2 lists the backbone designs used for each of the problems analyzed. The results obtained for these cases are shown in Table 3.

Problems 6-10 are done using only two subnets of size 12 but with the same back-bone designs. The results are listed in Table 4.

Figure 3. Process Flow for MC Simulation

Table 1. Local Subnets

Local Subnet (s)	Design (\mathbf{N}_s^L)
1	{1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8}
2	{9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16}
3	{17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24}

Table 2. Back-bone Subnets

Problem	Back-bone 1 Design (\mathbf{N}_1^B)	Back-bone 2 Design (\mathbf{N}_2^B)
1	{1,9,17}	{2,10,18}
2	{1,2,9,10,17,18}	{1,2,9,10,17,18}
3	{1,2,9,10,17,18}	{3,4,11,12,19,20}
4	{1,2,3,9,10,11,17,18,19}	{4,5,6,12,13,14,20,21,22}
5	{1,2,3,4,9,10,11,12,17,18,19,20}	{5,6,7,8,13,14,15,16,21,22,23,24}

Table 3. Results

Problem	$2\hat{TR}_m(t)$	$A\hat{TR}_m(t)$	$Ao\hat{TR}_m(t)$
24 Node MAWN with 8 node local subnets			
1	0.4384	0.0212	0.0580
2	0.8548	0.1948	0.4604
3	0.8728	0.2344	0.4452
4	0.9292	0.3252	0.4824
5	0.9876	0.5176	0.5956

Table 4.Results(2)

Prob-lem	$2\hat{TR}_m(t)$	$A\hat{TR}_m(t)$	$Ao\hat{TR}_m(t)$
24 Node MAWN with 8 node local subnets			
6	0.5472	0.0748	0.1800
7	0.9328	0.1956	0.4604
8	0.9320	0.2276	0.4312
9	0.9444	0.3380	0.5068
10	0.9852	0.5472	0.6392

4 ANALYSIS AND CONCLUSIONS

For these 10 problems, the results indicate that a cluster-based MAWN with fewer local subnets result in higher reliability. Similarly, when the cardinality of back-bone subnet node sets is increased reliability improves. This behavior is supported by the increasing values of reliability for each set of designs; $1 \rightarrow 5$, $5 \rightarrow 10$.

The results also show that when back-bone subnets are diverse with respect to each other, MAWN reliability increases across metrics. The inverse is also true, when back-bone networks share a high number of nodes the reliability seems to decrease. This behavior is evidence by comparing problems 2 and 3. The same quantity of back-bone radios are used in both problems but, in problem 3, total number of nodes with back-bone capability is increased.

In Problem #2 the AoTR increases because the nodes selected as members of each back-bone are the same. The reason for this is that in Problem #2 there exist nodes that have triple redundancy because they have one local and two back-bone radios for a total of three radios. This makes it more probable that these nodes will be operating and connected; for those without a back-bone they are most likely to be disconnected due to their own failure.

On the other hand, in Problem #3 more nodes are connected to any back-bone increasing the probability they'll be connected and increasing the number of operational nodes by providing multiple radios on more platforms. Thus, the increased ATR.

A method to formulate and analyze the reliability of a cluster-based MAWN is presented, adapting and extending the previous publications by Cook and Ramirez-Marquez [8-12]. The problem formulation is presented and adapts to the unique attributes of ad-hoc networks, specifically those associated with cluster-based MAWN. This has a significant contribution to the ability to design for the reliability of the MAWN and identification critical nodes. In addition, this paper includes and redefines reliability metrics applicable and appropriate for measurement of MAWN reliability; namely, two-terminal reliability, all-terminal reliability, and all-operating terminal reliability.

Of greatest significance, this method provides the ability to determine the influence on reliability due to changes of the back-bone assignments or alterations to the quantity of back-bone enabled nodes. Conclusive relationships between cluster size, back-bone node quantity, back-bone node assignment, and reliability metrics have been demonstrated and explained.

In practice, this method will be utilized to analyze various design solutions (different back-bone assignments or cluster sizes) to determine the more reliable design or if a specific design meets the reliability objective. Ultimately, the method may be used to design a cluster-based network to meet reliability targets.

Next, the authors plan to extend this work to develop an optimization routine built upon this Monte Carlo analysis technique. The decision variables of this optimization will be the back-bone assignments with constrained cost and/or weight limiting the total number of back-bones allowed. This will provide even more utility to the systems engineer employing the method because it will eliminate the current trial and error nature of design in favor of assured convergence on a design solution.

It is worth noting that the method developed and this on-going research is motivated by and directly applicable to DoD communications networks. The benefits of ad-hoc networking (namely flexibility and mobility) are leveraged for most tactical data communications. The reliance on communications networks for DoD systems is ever growing and thereby the reliability of ad-hoc networks is paramount. It is expected that this work will help improve the reliability of such networks in the future.

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